

DETERMINANTS OF SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING ADOPTION AMONG NIGERIAN SMEs

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October 30, 2018

Abstract

Effective use of Social Media Marketing (SMM) has been identified as the catalyst for enhancing economic growth and gaining competitive advantage among Small and Medium scale Enterprises (SMEs) in the 21st century. However, despite the glaring importance of the technology, some developing countries like Nigeria have records of low level social media marketing adoption among their small and medium scale enterprises. The purpose of this study is to carry out an empirical investigation to determine the factors specifically influencing the adoption of social media marketing among Nigerian SMEs. Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) framework will be integrated with Social Exchange Theory (SET) to develop the conceptual model for the research work. Most of the existing studies that attempt to assess the influencing factors of social media marketing adoption by small and medium enterprises did not take cognizance of social exchange factors. Therefore, this research work will attempt to fill this gap in the literature by adding some social exchange factors (perceived risk and perceived benefits) among the determinants of Social Media Marketing adoption by small and medium enterprises.

Keywords: Social Media Marketing, Adoption, Nigeria, SMEs

1 INTRODUCTION

Social Media Marketing enhances SME's capability to keep in touch with their consumers and respond to their needs and requests. SMM is considered as the fastest-growing marketing channel in the world. Social media marketing has been identified as a critical success factor for small businesses [1]. Embracing social media marketing is no longer a strategic business option, but a necessity, and a huge opportunity for SME's.

Social media was defined as a group of Internet-based applications that were built on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0, and allow the creation and exchange of user generated contents [2]. Social Media Marketing on the other hand refers to the process of using social media channel(s) to perform business activities [3]. SMM is being used by SMEs in their marketing activities because it has the great outcome on productivities, inexpensive position and customer value for less cost and time.

SMEs are playing important role in the creation of equitable distribution of income at national level and improving global competitiveness at international level [1]. SMM has been acknowledge as a modern tool that brings numerous benefits to SME's by providing them with access to geographically dispersed target customers, enhancing their economic growth, competitive advantage and administrative efficiencies [4].

In spite of the numerous benefits that SME’s drive through the adoption of SMM, Nigerian SMEs are slow in the adoption of the technology. Surprisingly, social media channels are widely used by Nigerian consumers most especially Facebook. According to Africa Internet and Facebook users population statistics, 2018, Nigeria has the largest social media users in Africa. Facebook is the most popular social network in the country. This is an indication of great SMM opportunity for Nigerian SMEs. However, adoption of SMM Marketing by Nigerian SMEs is still lower than expected[5]. As rightly observed by [6], lack of technology adoption by SMEs in Nigeria is one of the reasons for their failure. More than 50% of Nigerian SMEs fail within their first 5 years of operation with marketing often cited as the major reason.

An exploratory research conducted by [7] showed that the major marketing benefit that Nigerian SME’s achieve through the adoption of web 2.0 marketing is increase in brand awareness and revenue. Another study was conducted by [8] to examine the effect of SMM on the performance of SMEs in Ota-metropolis, Nigeria. Existing literature has revealed that factors influencing the adoption of SMM by SMEs vary among developing countries [9]. This has therefore indicated the need for determining the factors that specifically influence the decision making process of Nigerian SMEs on social media marketing adoption with a view to come up with recommendations that can be used to enhance the level of adoption of the technology among Nigerian SME’s to enable them to compete favorably in both local and international markets.

2 PROPOSED WORK

The proposed research work is intended to carry out an empirical study to specifically determine the factors that influence the adoption of social media marketing among Nigerian SME’s. Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) framework was integrated with the Social Exchange Theory to develop the following conceptual framework for the proposed research work.

Figure 1. TOE-SET based model of SMM adoption by SMEs

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